

Thermal-hydraulic analysis and uncertainty quantification application of a DBA sequence in a generic iPWR using MELCOR code

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ABSTRACT

In light of prospective licensing frameworks for Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), the international scientific community is investigating the applicability of Severe Accident (SA) integral codes to simulate SMR-specific phenomenology under postulated transient scenarios. Among light-water SMR concepts, the integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) – deriving from the well-proven and established large Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology – is characterized by an integral configuration and the adoption of passive safety systems. Within this framework, the Horizon Project “Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident” (SASPAM – SA), coordinated by ENEA (Italy), aims to investigate the applicability and transfer of operating large LWR knowledge and know-how to iPWRs because of the envisaged SA and Emergency Planning Zone European licensing needs. In this view, the present study investigates the capability of the integral code MELCOR, developed by Sandia National Laboratory for the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission, to reproduce the thermal–hydraulic phenomenology of a postulated Design Basis Accident scenario in a generic iPWR design. This scenario consists of a Loss of Coolant Accident due to the double-ended guillotine break of a Direct Vessel Injection line. To investigate the uncertainty of the code on the thermal–hydraulic phenomena characterizing such scenario, a Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty (BEPU) approach based on the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty has been applied to quantify the impact of fourteen uncertain input parameters related to boundary conditions and passive safety systems operation on safety-relevant Figures of Merit (FOMs): peak of maximum cladding temperature, minimum collapsed coolant level in the core region and the maximum containment pressure. The results demonstrate that the MELCOR code is able to predict the expected phenomenology characterizing the transient (passive injection, passive decay heat removal, etc.), and the uncertainty analysis provides insights into the influence of passive safety systems’ operation on the evolution of the selected FOMs.

1. Introduction

Because of the near-term deployment of future Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs), Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are currently regarded as one of the most promising solutions (Iaea, 2005). Characterized by a lower

nominal power output than conventional nuclear reactors, SMRs enable greater operational flexibility and improved inherent safety. Among light water SMRs, integral Pressurized Water Reactors (iPWRs) are considered one of the most promising technological options due to the operational experience and lessons learned from large-scale Light Water

Abbreviations: ADS, Automatic Depressurization System; BEPU, Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty; CRDM, Control Rod Drive Mechanism; CRP, Coordinated Research Program; DBA, Design Basis Accident; DC, Downcomer; DEC, Design Extended Conditions; DID, Defence-in-Depth; DVI, Direct Vessel Injection; DW, Drywell; EBT, Emergency Boration Tank; EHRS, Emergency Heat Removal System; EPZ, Emergency Planning Zone; FOM, Figure Of Merit; HX, Heat eXchanger; IAEA, International Atomic Energy Agency; iPWR, integral Pressurized Water Reactor; IRIS, International Reactor Innovative and Secure; LGMS, Long-Term Gravity Make-up System; LOCA, Loss Of Coolant Accident; LP, Lower Plenum; LWR, Light Water Reactor; NPP, Nuclear Power Plant; PDF, Probability Density Function; PhW, Phenomenological Window; PRZ, Pressurizer; PSS, Pressure Suppression System; QT, Quench Tank; R&D, Research and Development; RC, Reactor Cavity; RCP, Reactor Coolant Pump; RCS, Reactor Coolant System; RI-DC, Riser-DownComer; RPV, Reactor Pressure Vessel; RWST, Refueling Water Storage Tank; SA, Severe Accident; SG, Steam Generator; SMR, Small Modular Reactor; SNAP, Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package; SNL, Sandia National Laboratories; SOT, Start Of the Transient; UP, Upper Plenum; USNRC, United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission; UT, Uncertainty Tool.

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Reactors (LWRs). The technology of iPWRs shares several characteristics with the current generation of LWRs, while also exhibiting features typical of their advanced design. Among these peculiarities are low-pressure phenomena, interactions between the containment and the Reactor Coolant System (RCS), and phenomena specific to their components and systems. In general, they are characterized by the adoption of an integral Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) containing all the RCS components and, in general, by the use of passive safety systems.

In the European context, there is a growing interest in iPWR technology, and several countries have started preparatory measures and Research and Development (R&D) programs to aim at supporting their licensing processes. Recently, in Europe multiple projects have been developed or are in progress funded by European Commission to support SMR deployment (European Commission, EASI-SMR; European Commission, ELSMOR; European Commission, HARMONIZE; European Commission, MCSAFER; European Commission, PASTELS; European Commission, SASPAM-SA; European Commission, TANDEM). Furthermore, additional initiatives as the SMR pre-partnership (Nucleareurope), which has now concluded, and the European Industrial Alliance on Small Modular Reactors (Commission, 2025), have also taken place in Europe.

Advanced designs, such as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large LWRs and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages and reinforcing the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD) principle (SMR, 2018; Iaea, 1996). However, independent features for preventing and mitigating a Severe Accident (SA) sequence have to be included in its design together with the off-site emergency response, according to DiD levels 4 and 5. Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to SA need to be postulated and deterministically studied.

Within this framework, the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project (European Commission, SASPAM-SA; SASPAM-SA; Zenodo, SASPAM-SA; ETSO, SASPAM-SA; Herranz et al., 2025; Mascari et al., 2024), coordinated by ENEA (Italy), aims to investigate the applicability and transfer of the operating large LWRs knowledge and know-how to the near-term deployment of iPWR, because of the SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) European licensing analyses needs. Within this framework, the main objective of the project is the assessment of the capabilities of internationally recognized computational tools – both European and non-European codes, widely used in Europe – to simulate the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs under SA conditions and to predict the associated radiological consequences.

To maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project, two generic iPWR design concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with current operating reactors, have been selected within the project. Design 1 is characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of about 60 MWe. Instead, Design 2 is characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment, and an electric power of about 300 MWe. These two generic concepts include the main iPWR design features of the most promising designs ready to go on the European market. Then, they allow for assessing in a wider way the capability of computational tools to simulate the typical phenomena occurring in iPWRs. It is underlined that the objective of the project is not to assess the generic reactor designs selected, but, on the other hand, based on the project findings, the project aims to allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favoured designs under postulated SA conditions.

In this context, the international nuclear community involved in the development of Deterministic Safety Analyses (DSAs) in the SA domain is focusing on evaluating the applicability of state-of-the-art SA integral codes, such as ASTEC (Chatelard, 2016) and MELCOR (Humphries et al., 2023; Humphries et al., 2023), to iPWRs. These codes are already widely used for simulating operating NPPs under transient conditions and are capable of modelling the complex multi-physics phenomena characterizing a SA scenario. Among them, thermal-hydraulic phenomena are of

primary importance, as they drive the progression of the accident and strongly influence typical SA phenomena and processes such as fuel degradation and melting, hydrogen generation, and the release of fission products within the containment in both gaseous and aerosol forms.

As previously discussed, iPWRs are characterized by novel design features and the adoption of a full passive safety strategy using passive safety systems. Experimental campaigns such as PERSEO (Ferri et al., 2005) and OSU-MASLWR (Mascari, 2012), VISTA-ITL (Park, 2014) and FESTA (Park, 2012) have been specifically carried out to establish a comprehensive experimental database for the validation of thermal-hydraulic system codes (Mascari et al., 2015). Several validation studies applying these experimental datasets are available (Mascari et al., 2011; Mascari, 2016; Chung et al., 2014) and (Pottorf et al., 2009). In this view, studies on passive safety systems with the SA integral codes MELCOR (Mascari, et al., 2023; Kecek, 2023; Yoon et al., 2017) and ASTEC (Maccari et al., 2021) have been underlined.

Given the development of DSA in the SA domain for iPWR licensing purposes, the assessment of the capability of SA integral codes to model iPWR thermal-hydraulic phenomenology related to passive safety systems represents a crucial aspect, since typical phenomena, such as natural circulation, could strongly affect the transient progression and the estimation of the consequences. Furthermore, it is a key aspect because the operation or partial or non-operation (e.g., functional failure or non-operation of the activation valves) of passive safety systems strongly affects the transient evolution both under Design Basis Accident (DBA) and Design Extension Conditions (DEC) scenarios, including SAs. In this regard, several activities have been conducted covering DBA (Maccari et al., 2021; Principato, 2025) and DEC scenarios (Maccari et al., 2023; Malicki and Lind, 2024; Malicki and Lind, 2024).

In this view, the main objective of the present work, developed in the framework of the SASPAM-SA project, is to have a first insight into the capability of the SA integral code MELCOR, developed by Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) for the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (USNRC), to simulate the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena during a DBA scenario in a generic iPWR design. In more detail, Design 2 has been selected. Furthermore, the activity aims to gain insights into the uncertainty of the MELCOR code on the prediction of the typical thermal-hydraulic phenomena during the transient sequence. For this reason, the uncertainty quantification analysis of the results adopting the Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty (BEPU) approach has been conducted (Iaea, 2008). To carry out the study, the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty methodology (Glaeser, 2008) has been adopted. The present uncertainty methodology has been used in several works in the thermal-hydraulics field (Bersano et al., 2020; Alcaro et al., 2021; Agnello et al., 2177; Bersano et al., 2685) and in the SA domain (Mascari et al., 2024; Brumm et al., 2025; Agnello et al., 2025; Garbarini, n.d.; Maccari et al., 2023; Coindreau et al., 2023). A Python-based Uncertainty Tool (UT) has been used: it has been developed starting from the experience matured along the Management and Uncertainty of Severe Accident (MUSA) project (Agnello et al., 2025; Herranz, 2021; Herranz, 2025) and finalized in the framework of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) Coordinated Research Program (CRP; Garbarini, n.d.; IAEA, 2024; IAEA). The uncertainty analysis has been conducted considering three Figures of Merit (FOMs) relevant to reactor safety. The selected uncertain input parameters related to initial and boundary conditions and passive safety systems have been selected based on literature and engineering judgment.

2. Description of the generic iPWR design

The chosen generic iPWR design is characterized by a thermal power of 1000 MW_{th} and an electrical output of 300 MW_e. This concept adopts an integral RPV hosted by a dry steel containment, which is divided into two regions: the Drywell (DW) and the Reactor Cavity (RC). Inside the RPV are placed all the Reactor Coolant System (RCS) components, such as the Pressurizer (PRZ), compact Steam Generators (SGs), and the

Fig. 2.1. View of the RPV of the generic iPWR (Gabrielli et al., 2024).

Reactor Coolant Pumps (RCPs). Fig. 2.1 provides a schematic view of the RPV of the selected iPWR design, highlighting the integral configuration of the main RCS components.

The primary coolant first flows through the core and then crosses the riser region (surrounded by the extended core barrel). At the top of the riser, it is directed radially into the upper annular plenum, which houses the RCPs' suction region. The coolant is pumped by RCPs to the corresponding SG module. The SGs are characterized by the adoption of compact SGs (in particular, helical-coil tubes SGs have been selected). After flowing through the SG modules, the primary coolant flows downward through the Downcomer (DC) region, surrounding the core, to the Lower Plenum (LP). Finally, it returns to flow up to the reactor core.

As specified above, the iPWR design features a full passive mitigation strategy based on the use of several passive safety features. To comprehensively assess the capabilities of computational codes in simulating typical phenomena driven by the operation of passive safety systems, the following safety functions and safety systems have been considered:

- *Natural circulation within RPV*: the reactor is designed to sustain core cooling by promoting natural circulation of primary coolant within RPV.¹
- *Passive Decay heat removal*: dedicated passive systems are designed to ensure the removal of residual core power following the reactor shutdown during transient scenarios.

¹ During potential accidental conditions, following the primary pump trip, the flow in the RPV is driven by natural circulation. In case of a LOCA with subsequent RPV level reduction, natural circulation may be hindered when the level reduces below the upper connection between the riser outlet and the downcomer inlet. Therefore, additional connections may be present between the RPV riser and downcomer at a lower elevation to enable natural circulation at reduced RPV level.

- *Primary automatic depressurization*: automatic depressurization systems allow the depressurization of the RPV, thereby enabling the activation of passive emergency core cooling systems.
- *Passive High-pressure safety injection*: these systems, operating at high-pressure conditions, restore the primary coolant in case of a Loss Of Coolant Accident (LOCA) by injecting borated water into the RPV.
- *Passive Low-pressure safety injection*: low-pressure safety systems are designed to inject coolant into the primary systems at low-pressure conditions, typically after a system depressurization.
- *Passive Containment pressure suppression*: the steam generated inside the containment during a possible accidental transient is directed to a large suppression pool, by proper connection, where it is condensed.
- *Passive Flooding of the cavity*: passive flooding of the Reactor Cavity (RC) provides external cooling of the RPV's Lower Head (LH). It represents a key mitigation strategy for the in-vessel melt retention during SA accident conditions.

Fig. 2.2 (Gabrielli et al., 2024) provides an integrated view of the RPV, containment regions and the passive safety systems configuration with the corresponding safety functions listed above. In this regard, Table 2.1 summarizes the safety functions considered and discussed previously, along with the corresponding passive safety systems implemented in the selected design to fulfil each specific function.

3. Description of the iPWR MELCOR input deck

3.1. The MELCOR code

MELCOR (Humphries et al., 2023; Humphries et al., 2023) is a fully integrated SA code able to simulate the thermal-hydraulic phenomena in steady and transient conditions and the main SA phenomena characterizing the RPV, the RC, the containment, and the confinement buildings typical of LWR. The code is based on a finite-difference resolution method for the conservation equations of Control Volumes (CVs) and can be used with the Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package (SNAP) (Inc, 2021) for the development of the nodalization and for the post-processing of the data.

The code presents a modular structure based on packages simulating different phenomena of a reactor transient. Among the packages characterizing MELCOR, the Control Volume Hydrodynamic (CVH) and Flow Path (FL) packages are responsible for the thermal-hydraulic behaviour of liquid water and gases and provide boundary conditions for the other packages. The Heat Structure (HS) packages model the heat transfer. The COR package evaluates the degradation phenomena involving the fuel and other core structures, including the LH. Then, the RadioNuclide (RN) package is dedicated to the release and transport modelling of radionuclides in gas and aerosol form. The MELCOR code v2023 has been used for the calculation reported in the present manuscript.

3.2. The iPWR MELCOR nodalization

Considering the main safety features and systems discussed above, a generic International Reactor Innovative and Secure (IRIS) («INTERNATIONAL REACTOR INNOVATIVE AND SECURE, IRIS Plant Overview,» October, 2002) iPWR design has been considered as a reference to develop the MELCOR input deck (Gabrielli et al., 2024). It has been built up in the framework of the SASPAM-SA project without using proprietary data, and it has been developed by scaling the available data of the SPES-3 experimental facility (Carrelli et al., 2009; Ferri and Congiu, 2008) as well as by engineering evaluation from public general data available.

The model combines a trade-off between the computational time and a detailed prediction capability of the transient thermal-hydraulic and core degradation phenomenology. The two DVI lines and the two trains

Fig. 2.2. Layout of the RPV, containment regions and passive safety systems configuration of the generic iPWR. (Gabrielli et al., 2024).

Table 2.1

Passive safety systems of the generic iPWR.

Safety function	Passive safety system
Natural circulation within RPV	<i>Riser-Downcomer (RI-DC) valves</i> : these valves connect the riser and the SG primary side at mid-riser elevation.
Decay heat removal	<i>Emergency Heat Removal System (EHRS)</i> : the system is composed of four cooling loops operating in natural circulation. It connects the secondary side of SGs and submerged Heat exchangers (HXs) within the <i>Refueling Water Storage Tanks (RWSTs)</i> , acting as a heat sink.
Primary automatic depressurization	<i>Automatic Depressurization System (ADS)</i> : it is composed of two different valves trains. The ADS stage-1 is activated at an early stage of the transient to depressurize the RPV and discharge primary coolant into a <i>Quench Tank (QT)</i> . The ADS stage-2 directly connects the RPV with the containment to equalize pressure.
High-pressure safety injection	<i>Emergency Boration Tanks (EBTs)</i> : They are composed of two tanks connected at the top and at the bottom by two Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) lines, with the RPV. When the system is activated, natural circulation occurs between the RPV and the tank.
Low-pressure safety injection	<i>Long-Term Gravity Make-up System (LGMS)</i> : They are composed of elevated tanks injecting water into the RPV by gravity through two DVI lines.
Containment pressure suppression	<i>Pressure Suppression System (PSS)</i> : It consists of 2 water tanks connected to the containment through pipes named PSS-vent pipes, partially submerged in the PSS. Following a LOCA, the steam from the primary enters the containment and then, through the PSS vents, condenses in the pools. They are hydraulically connected to the LGMSs.
Flooding of the RC	<i>PSS and PSS-vent pipes</i> : Because the DW's pressure decreases below the PSS pressure, water inside the PSSs is forced upward through the PSS-vent pipes and fills the RC.

of passive safety systems have been modelled separately. Each line includes the EBT, the PSS, the PSS-vent and the LGMS. Fig. 3.1 shows the nodalization of the two trains of passive safety systems, connected to the two DVI lines.

The RPV has been modelled with different CVH CVs, coupled with FL flow path and HSS, including the LP, the reactor core, the core by-pass, the riser, the Upper Plenum (UP), the SGs and the DC. Fig. 3.2 illustrates the MELCOR CVH FL and COR nodalization adopted for the RPV,

including the section of quench pipe and quench tank.

To simplify the model, the eight SGs have been modelled as an equivalent one, with four CVH CVs on the primary side and eight CVs on the secondary side. The reactor core has been modelled by a single CV coupled with the corresponding COR package nodalization characterized by sixteen axial levels and six radial rings.

Fig. 3.3 provides a detailed view of the MELCOR CVH and FL nodalization for the containment region and EHRS and RWST. The containment has been modelled by means of two main CVH CV representing the DW region and the RC, respectively. The CV of DW represents the free gas volume surrounding the RPV, and it is thermally coupled with the external environment through HSS representing the containment internal steel shell. Furthermore, the CV of RC is coupled with the MELCOR CAV package to allow the simulation of cavity flooding and heat exchange with LH structures. The EHRS has been modelled with a set of CVH CVs hydraulically connected to the secondary side of the SGs. The loop is connected thermally with the RWST, which represents the ultimate heat sink connected to the environment. In this regard, the equivalent EHRS HX has been modelled with six CVs thermally coupled with six CVs of the RWST. In total, nine CVs have been considered to model the RWST.

The double-ended guillotine break of one DVI line has been simulated by using two independent flow paths, as also indicated in Fig. 3.2. The first one connects the DC region of the RPV to the RC CV, representing the rupture of the DVI line and its connection with the primary system. The second flow path connects the passive safety systems associated with the broken DVI train (EBT, LGMS and PSS) to the RC, ensuring a consistent representation of the hydraulic separation between the intact and broken passive safety systems trains. This modelling approach allows the representation of mass and energy release into the containment following the break, preserving the asymmetric behaviour between the intact and broken passive safety system trains.

4. Description of the reference case

The reference scenario is a LOCA initiated by the double-ended guillotine break of one of the two DVI lines (Carrelli et al., 2009; Maccari et al., 2021; Ferri, 2010; Achilli et al., 2012). The DVI lines connect the two passive systems' trains to the RPV, at an elevation located below the SGs outlet in the primary side, as shown before in Fig. 2.2. It has been modelled in the MELCOR nodalization, as shown previously in Fig. 3.2.

Fig. 3.1. MELCOR CVH and FL nodalization of the passive safety systems.

Fig. 3.2. MELCOR CVH, FL and COR nodalization of the RPV.

Fig. 3.3. MELCOR CVH nodalization of the containment, RWST and EHRS system.

Considering the design layout, the selected LOCA is the worst accidental scenario since it is located at the lowest possible RPV location.

The reference calculation has been performed considering an initial steady-state analysis of 2000 s in nominal conditions. In this regard, Table 4.1 presents the main thermal–hydraulic parameters of the steady-state analysis. For each parameter, both absolute and relative deviations with respect to reference values presented in (Maccari et al., 2021), have been evaluated. The steady-state calculation results have been considered acceptable, with, in general, a deviation of less than 5% considering the relative deviation.

The Start Of the Transient (SOT) has been considered at $t = 0$ s with the opening of the break. The transient analysis has been performed for 20,000 s. The transient evolution can be divided into three main Phenomenological Windows (PhWs), which are described in the sections below.

4.1. PhW 1: Blowdown phase

The beginning of the transient is driven by the blowdown of the RPV

Table 4.1
Steady-state calculation of thermal–hydraulic parameters.

Parameter	Unit [-]	Reference	MELCOR	Discrepancy ¹
PRZ pressure	[MPa]	15.5	15.5	0.00
Primary mass flow rate	[kg/s]	4700	4700	0.00
Core bypass mass flow rate	[kg/s]	199.8	204	2.05
Inlet core temperature	[K]	566.0	569.7	0.65
Outlet core temperature	[K]	603.0	605.7	0.45
Core Power	[MW _{th}]	1000	1000	0
Total SGs feedwater mass flow rate	[kg/s]	502.8	500.5	0.46
SG feedwater pressure	[MPa]	6.5	6.22	4.31
SG feedwater inlet temperature	[K]	497.0	497.0	0.00
SG steam outlet pressure	[MPa]	5.83	5.89	1.03
SG steam outlet temperature	[K]	590.0	593.0	0.51

Discrepancy in the Table 4.1 has been calculated as the percentage difference between the parameters evaluated by the code and the reference values.

and the consequent primary coolant discharge to the containment. Fig. 4.1 presents the mass flow rate of primary coolant discharged through the break, primary pressure, secondary pressure, containment pressure and pressure of passive safety systems during PhW 1. The code predicts a maximum mass flow rate of about 110 kg/s. Consequently, with the discharge of primary coolant from the RPV, the primary pressure decreases and the containment pressure increases. This phenomenology is predicted by the code and shown in Fig. 4.1.

The containment pressurization determines the transfer of hot steam-gas mixture from the containment to the PSSs through the PSS-vent lines, which allows the pressurization of the containment to be limited. Since PSSs and LGMSs are hydraulically connected to the containment, their pressure increases following the pressure trend of the containment, as presented in Fig. 4.1.

At about 43 s after the SOT, the containment high-pressure set-point is achieved and the reactor SCRAM is activated, with the isolation of the secondary side of SGs and the opening of the EHRS loops.² Due to SGs' secondary side isolation, the secondary pressure increase occurs, and it is predicted by the code as presented in Fig. 4.1. After the peak, the secondary pressure begins to decrease due to the EHRS actuation. The action of the passive system, driven by natural circulation, allows the transfer of power from the RPV to the RWST. Fig. 4.2 presents the power balance in the system, the coolant level in the core and cavity, the maximum cladding temperature and RWST water temperature during PhW 1. In particular, the code predicts a peak of power transmitted to the RWST water storage equal to about 100 MW.

Due to the blowdown, the collapsed coolant level in the RPV decreases, and the coolant level in the PRZ reaches the low-level setpoint at about 122 s after the break. Then, RCPs coast down, and the automatic opening of the Riser-DownComer (RI-DC) check valves is triggered. At this stage of the transient, the flow rate inside the RPV is sustained only by natural circulation. The collapsed coolant level inside the RPV

² For the analyses presented in the paper, because of the nodalization structure (only one equivalent EHRS), the logic is simplified and only one actuation of EHRS is considered.

Fig. 4.1. Break mass flow rate, primary pressure, secondary pressure, containment pressure and passive safety systems pressure evolutions during PhW 1.

continues to decrease due to the rupture, leading to the TAF uncovering at about 175 s after the SOT, as shown in Fig. 4.2.

When the PRZ pressure reaches the low-pressure set-point, predicted by the code at about 148 s after the SOT, the ADS Stage-1 is opened, and the EBTs start to inject water. The EBT located in the broken passive safety systems train injects water inside the RC; then the EBT located in the intact passive safety systems train injects water inside the RPV. The opening of the ADS Stage-1 allows the discharge of steam from PRZ to the QT, enhancing the primary depressurization and accelerating the pressure equalization between the RPV and the containment. This phenomenon is predicted by the code and shown in Fig. 4.1. Furthermore, the actuation of EHRS increases the energy removal from the primary system and then results in a decrease in primary pressure, as presented in Fig. 4.1.

The low RPV-Containment differential pressure signal activates at about 1884 s after the SOT and starts the injection of water by LGMSs. In a similar way as described before for EBTs, the LGMS located in the broken passive safety systems train injects water into the RC, and the EBT located in the intact passive safety systems train injects water inside the RPV. The pressure equalization between the containment and the RPV occurs at about 2000 s after the SOT, as indicated also in Fig. 4.1. The reactor core uncover and core heat-up are prevented by the discharge through the undamaged DVI line by the injection of EBT and

LGMS. In fact, during PhW 1, the maximum cladding temperature decreases and, due to the EHRS activation, the RWST water temperature increases, as presented in Fig. 4.2.

4.2. PhW 2: Core reflood phase and cavity filling

Because of the steam condensation occurring in the DW's metallic inner walls and the heat removed by the EHRS system, the pressure in the containment decreases below the PSSs/LGMSs pressure after the 1st RPV-Containment pressure equalization. Fig. 4.3 shows the pressure evolution in the system, mass flow rate through the PSSs vent pipe and the collapsed coolant level in the core and cavity during PhW 2. The collapsed water level reaches the TAF again at about 3000 s after the break, as shown in Fig. 4.3. The pressure inversion between the containment and PSSs/LGMSs determines the rise of water level within the PSSs vent pipes and the injection of water into the containment at about 3010 s after the SOT, causing the increase of water level in the RC as shown in Fig. 4.3. The water level in the cavity reaches the DVI elevation at about 4000 s after the break, allowing for the initiation of long-term core flooding.

Fig. 4.2. Power balance, collapsed levels in the core and cavity and maximum cladding temperature and RWST water temperature evolutions during PhW 1.

4.3. PhW 3: Long-term cooling phase

The water injection by PSSs-vent pipes causes a decrease in containment pressure, which reaches the RPV pressure in the 2nd RPV-containment pressure equalization at about 3315 s after the SOT. The RPV pressure reaches equilibrium with the containment at about 5000 s after the break. The pressure inside PSSs/LGMSs systems is maintained higher than containment pressure, causing a 2nd PSS-vent pipe water injection at about 5375 s after the break and contributes to maintaining the water level within the RC. Fig. 4.4 presents the PSS vent pipe mass flow rate, collapsed levels in the core and cavity and the maximum cladding temperature during PhW 3.

The water in the RC allows the flooding of the core and its cooling in the long-term cooling phase. Therefore, the core temperature, in terms of maximum cladding temperature, continues to decrease as presented in Fig. 4.4. It is kept constant below 400 K for about 10,000 s after the SOT. Furthermore, the heat losses through the DW metal walls to the environment and the power extracted by the EHR systems allow the cooling down of the core. In this regard, the net effect of the power transmission from the core to RWST by the EHR system is the increase in water liquid temperature within RWST, presented in Fig. 4.4. At about 12,265 s after the break, the ADS Stage-2 is opened, allowing steam circulation between containment and RPV. Finally, Table 4.2 shows the main timings of the event characterizing the DBA sequence.

5. Uncertainty quantification methodology

Among the uncertainty methodologies developed in the past to conduct uncertainty quantification analyses (Iaea, 2008), the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty (Glaeser, 2008) is based, in general, on statistical approaches to correlate the input uncertainty, identified by the uncertain input parameters, to output uncertainty, expressed in the uncertainty of selected FOMs. Each uncertain input parameter is identified by a Probability Density Function (PDF), usually selected based on previous analyses, available experimental data, and engineering judgment (Stephens et al., 1993). A Monte Carlo random sampling of the uncertain input parameters is performed to define a number N of sets of values of the uncertain input parameters used to define N input decks used to start N code runs. Wilks's formula (Wilks, 1941; Wilks, 1942) can be used to determine the minimum number of code runs N based on the requested probability content γ and confidence level β . If multiple FOMs p are analysed, N is calculated using Wald's formula (Wald, 1943), presented below for the one-sided tolerance interval:

$$\beta = \sum_{j=0}^{N-p} \binom{N}{j} \alpha^j (1-\alpha)^{N-j} \quad (1)$$

More details on the statistical aspects can be found in (Guba et al.,

Fig. 4.3. Pressures, mass flow rates through PSSs vent pipes and collapsed levels evolutions during PhW 2.

2003). As well as assessing the uncertainty width of FOMs, the mean, median, standard deviation and coefficient of variation are calculated in this work. To gain insights about the statistical correlation between the FOMs and the selected uncertain input parameters, the simple and simple rank correlation coefficients are computed (Agnello et al., 2177; Bersano et al., 2020; Gamble and Swiler, 2016; Rodgers and Nicewander, 1987).

The UT used in this uncertainty application, shown in Fig. 5.1, can perform all the steps needed for the development of an uncertainty analysis (Garbarini, n.d). The user specifies the N number of code runs desired as well as the uncertainty parameters selected for analysis, and the tool, by sampling, creates the N sets of parameters to be replaced in an input-deck template. After executing the code, the tool manages the FOMs calculated data extraction by using the AptBatch executable (Technology, 2021) and then develops the statistical analysis of the results and the post-processing.

6. Results of the uncertainty analysis

6.1. Statistical analysis

The goal of the present study is not to perform a comprehensive uncertainty study in terms of uncertain input parameters and FOMs selected from a licensing perspective. On the other hand, the main

objective of the work is the development of a full uncertainty analysis on an iPWR design using the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty in order to give key insights about the statistical correlation between uncertain input parameters and the FOMs.

Following as done in (Agnello et al., 2177), the FOMs selected for the present analysis are:

- Peak of maximum cladding temperature after 1000 s from the SOT (referred to as FOM_1)³;
- Minimum collapsed coolant level in the core region (referred to as FOM_2);
- Maximum containment pressure (referred to as FOM_3).

The FOMs selected play a crucial role in the understanding of the safety conditions of the plant during a transient accidental event. The uncertain input parameters, listed in Table 6.1, have been selected and extrapolated from (Alcaro et al., 2021; Perez, 2011; Maccari et al., 2021)

³ Considering the reference case, the maximum cladding temperature during the transient occurs at the SOT and its value is influenced by initial conditions of the system rather than by transient evolution. Accordingly, the peak of maximum cladding temperature at 1000 s has been selected as a more representative metric of for assessing code uncertainty in the transient phenomenology.

Fig. 4.4. Maximum cladding temperature, core and cavity collapsed water levels and RWST temperature.

Table 4.2

Main events characterizing the reference case.

Event	PhW [-]	Time [s]
Break	1	0
High Containment pressure signal (SCRAM, isolation of SGs, EHRS activation)		41
Low PRZ water level signal (pump coast down and RI-DC opening)		122
Low PRZ pressure signal (ADS Stage-1 opening, EBTs opening)		148
Low Delta P RPV-Containment (LGMS opening)		1884
1st RPV-containment pressure equalization		2000
Core water level reaches the TAF	2	3000
1st Water injection from PSSs-vent pipes		3010
2nd RPV-containment pressure equalization		3315
Cavity level reaches the DVI elevation		3950
2nd Water injection from PSSs-vent pipes	3	5405
Low LGMSs mass signal (ADS Stage-2 opening)		12,265

and based on engineering judgment.

Considering equation (1), 129 code runs have been considered to reach a probability γ and confidence level β of 95% for each FOM.

In Table 6.2, based on the analyses, the main statistical parameters characterizing the FOMs have been shown:

- The FOM_1 is characterized by a mean value of 504.74 K and an uncertainty width of 42.77 K, with a standard deviation of 8.23 K;
- The FOM_2 is characterized by a mean value of 4.46 m with an uncertainty band of 0.7 m and a standard deviation of 0.16 m;
- The FOM_3 by a mean value of 11.37E5 Pa, with an uncertainty width of 3.76E5 Pa and a standard deviation of 0.82E5 Pa.

In Fig. 6.1, the estimated PDF of the FOMs are shown. The x-axis shows standardized values, where 0 corresponds to the mean of the FOM. Negative values indicate results below the mean, and positive values above the mean. By standardizing each FOM, their shapes can be directly compared. The results highlight differences in the relative variability and distributional characteristics of each FOM. In particular, FOM_1 is more concentrated around its mean value (lower relative uncertainty), while FOM_2 and FOM_3 present wider distributions, suggesting higher sensitivity to uncertain input parameters.

6.2. Statistical correlation analysis

The simple and simple rank correlation coefficients have been calculated by using Pearson and Spearman's correlations for each FOM and each uncertain input parameter. They are shown in Fig. 6.2 and Fig. 6.3. From the statistical correlation analysis, it emerges that the FOM_1 presents a significant statistical correlation with the heat transfer

Fig. 5.1. Workflow of the UT (Garbarini, n.d.).

Table 6.1
Uncertain input parameters.

Uncertain input parameter	Nomenclature	Unit	PDF	Reference value	Lower and upper bound	Reference
Decay Power	P_1	[-] (multiplier)	Normal	1.0	Min 0.98 Max 1.02	(Perez, 2011)
Initial PRZ pressure	P_2	[Pa]	Normal	1.55E7	Min 1.54E7 Max 1.56E7	(Perez, 2011)
EBT initial temperature	P_3	[K]	Normal	321.9	Min 311.9 Max 331.9	(Perez, 2011)
LGMS initial temperature	P_4	[K]	Normal	321.9	Min 311.9 Max 331.9	(Perez, 2011)
Initial containment pressure	P_5	[Pa]	Uniform	1.013E5	Min 0.85E5 Max 1.15E5	(Perez, 2011)
RWST initial liquid level	P_6	[m]	Normal	9.0	Min 8.9390 Max 9.0610	(Alcaro et al., 2021)
RWST initial temperature	P_7	[K]	Uniform	293.0	Min 283.0 Max 303.0	(Maccari et al., 2021)
Heat Transfer Surface EHRs HXs	P_8	[-] (multiplier)	Uniform	1.0	Min 0.75 Max 1.25	(Alcaro et al., 2021)
Break Flow discharge coefficient	P_9	[-]	Uniform	0.7	Min 0.7 Max 1.0	Engineering Judgement
EHRs valves loss coefficient	P_10	[%]	Uniform	0	Min -100 Max +100	Engineering Judgement
EBT valves loss coefficient	P_11	[%]	Uniform	0	Min -100 Max +100	Engineering Judgement
LGMS valve loss coefficient	P_12	[%]	Uniform	0	Min -100 Max +100	Engineering Judgement
ADS Stage-1 loss Coefficient	P_13	[%]	Uniform	0	Min -100 Max +100	Engineering Judgement
ADS Stage-2 loss coefficient	P_14	[%]	Uniform	0	Min -100 Max +100	Engineering Judgement

Table 6.2
Statistical parameters of the FOMs.

Statistical parameter	FOM_1		FOM_2		FOM_3	
	Value	Unit	Value	Unit	Value	Unit
Mean	504.74	[K]	4.46	[m]	11.37E5	[Pa]
Median	505.53	[K]	4.47	[m]	11.32E5	[Pa]
Lower Bound	483.66	[K]	4.05	[m]	9.73E5	[Pa]
Upper Bound	526.43	[K]	4.75	[m]	13.49E5	[Pa]
Standard deviation	8.23	[K]	0.16	[m]	0.82E5	[Pa]
Coefficient of variation	0.016	[-]	0.037	[-]	0.072	[-]

surface of the EHRs HXs (negative correlation) and the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (positive correlation).

The FOM_2 presents a moderate statistical correlation with the initial

containment pressure (positive correlation), the heat transfer surface of EHRs HXs (negative correlation) and a significant correlation with the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (positive correlation).

Finally, FOM_3 presents, as expected, a moderate statistical correlation with the initial containment pressure (positive correlation), a moderate statistical correlation with the heat transfer surface of EHRs HXs (negative correlation) and a significant statistical correlation with the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (negative correlation).

The results shown before highlight that the uncertain input parameter ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient emerges as a particularly influential uncertain parameter across the FOMs. The significant statistical correlation indicates that variations in ADS Stage-1 valve loss coefficient propagate through the system, affecting the FOMs' results. Fig. 6.4 shows the relationship between the uncertain input parameter ADS Stage-1 valve loss coefficient and the standardized FOMs. Each point

Fig. 6.1. Calculated PDFs of the FOMs.

Fig. 6.4. Scatter plot of the FOMs and values of ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient.

Fig. 6.2. Simple correlation coefficient.

Fig. 6.3. Simple rank correlation coefficient.

represents one result of the N code runs in a z-score standardization. The fitted regression lines highlight, as expected from the calculation of the simple and simple rank coefficients, positive slopes for FOM_1 and FOM_2, whereas FOM_3 exhibits a negative trend.

6.3. Analysis of the uncertainty along the transient

To assess the uncertainty width of the code's results throughout the transient, the results of the N cases have been evaluated by comparing the maximum cladding temperature, the core collapsed coolant level and the containment pressure against the reference case and the main statistical parameters as mean, median, upper and lower bounds.

6.3.1. Maximum cladding temperature

The evolution of the uncertainty width of the maximum cladding temperature and the trend of standard deviation and coefficient of variation are presented in Fig. 6.5. During the PhW 1, the uncertainty band is relatively narrow, and it is characterized by a width of approximately 25 K within the first 1000 s. Between 1000 and 2000 s, the uncertainty band reaches its maximum amplitude of about 50 K. In this time window, some code runs present localized temperature peaks up to 525 K. These peaks are mainly due to particular runs in which the value of the loss coefficient of the EHRS presents a higher value than the reference value. It determines a lower mass flow rate due to natural circulation, and therefore, less power is transferred to the RWST. It causes an increase in cladding temperature until the injection of LGMSs. Due to the injection of LGMSs, the maximum cladding temperature decreases. These cases highlight how the action of LGMSs and, in particular, the EHRS plays a key role in mitigating transients in terms of key safety quantities, such as the maximum cladding temperature.

During PhW 1, the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation increase rapidly. It underlines a high sensitivity of the results' uncertainty during the blowdown and early heat transfer phases. The standard deviation peak is above 10 K, and the coefficient of variation reaches a value above 0.02. Fluctuations of the values of standard deviation and coefficient of variation during the final part of PhW 1 are consistent with the phenomenology occurring in PhW 1. In fact, in this time window, some of the results in terms of maximum cladding temperature present some peaks, as underlined above.

During PhW 2, at the beginning, the standard deviation and coefficient of variation decrease to a value of 6 K and 0.0125, respectively. Then, they increase again to a value of 10 K for the standard deviation and 0.016 for the coefficient of variation.

During the PhW 3, a gradual decrease in both the statistical parameters is observed. It means that the system is approaching quasi-steady state conditions, with the decay removal governed by long-term cooling systems. Overall, the statistical results on the maximum cladding temperature along the PhWs underline a higher uncertainty during the early phases of the transient.

6.3.2. Collapsed coolant level in the core region

Fig. 6.6⁴ shows the uncertainty width related to the core collapsed coolant level and the related standard deviation and coefficient of variation. Uncertainty width increases its amplitude along PhW 1 to a value of 1.20 m and reaches its maximum value at the beginning of PhW 3. Furthermore, the uncovering of the TAF during the transient presents a high uncertainty band in time terms, quantifiable on 4000 s, playing a key role in the cladding temperature behaviour as previously described.

The mean and median are characterized by a qualitative and quantitative similarity of their time trend with the reference case during PhW 1. After this time point, a qualitatively and quantitatively slightly

⁴ With reference to Fig. 6.6, the uncertainty band is cut just above the TAF as only the volume representative of the core region has been considered for the collapsed level.

different trend is highlighted. During PhW 1 the standard deviation rapidly rises, reaching a value of about 0.35–0.4 m, while the coefficient of variation presents a peak of approximately 0.06. The initial increase of both standard deviation and coefficient of variation is associated with the behaviour of the system during the blowdown. Characterized by significant divergence in core liquid level predictions by the code.

During PhW 2, both statistical metrics present an increase to a value of 0.8 m and 0.13, respectively. It indicates the highest uncertainty on code results, in terms of core collapsed coolant level, during the entire transient. The uncertainty is correlated to the reflooding dynamics, core uncovering and injections from passive systems, in particular, the LGMS system.

Then, during PhW 3, both standard deviation and coefficient of variation progressively decrease, reflecting a stabilization of the core level as far as the long-term cooling phase proceeds. In general, the uncertainties of the code in the core collapse coolant level are highest during the reflooding of the core, before reaching the TAF again.

6.3.3. Containment pressure

Concerning containment pressure, as presented in Fig. 6.7, the uncertainty band presents a maximum value at the beginning of PhW 3 equal to about 0.7 MPa. Moreover, the trend of the mean and the median is in qualitative and quantitative agreement with the reference case. Finally, the standard deviation and coefficient of variation are presented. During PhW 1, the containment pressure rises due to the blowdown, and this phase is characterized by a first peak of about 0.15 MPa for the standard deviation and a coefficient of variation of 0.25.

These values indicate a significant spread among the runs. The high variability reflects the sensitivity of the containment pressurization from the initial response of the systems; in particular, the EHRS removed power, and the ADS Stage-1 discharge mass flow rate plays a key role during the RPV depressurisation and consequently, on the other passive systems' actuation time.

Within the PhW 2, a second peak of both statistical metrics is observed. The standard deviation rises to over 0.2 MPa, and the coefficient of variation to a value of about 0.3. It reflects the strong influence of uncertain input parameters on phenomena related to PhW 2, such as pressure equalization and injections into the containment due to the PSS vent injection. It is important to highlight that, this phenomena is driven by pressure difference between the PSS system and the Containment environment; therefore, the pressure peak due to the amount of heat power dissipated by the EHRS system and due to the ADS discharge mass flow rate determine the time and the magnitude of the PSS reverse flow, influencing the reaching of the 2nd pressure equalization and the PhW 3.

On the other hand, during PhW 3, both standard deviation and coefficient of variation present a decreasing trend, with a value of 0.05 MPa and 0.10 for standard deviation and coefficient of variation, respectively.

6.4. Statistical correlation analysis along the transient

The statistical correlation analysis, using the simple and simple rank correlation coefficients, has also been carried out during the investigated PhWs of the transient.⁵ The most significant correlations have briefly explained below. Correlations limited in time and not significant have not been discussed since they need more investigations to confirm the physical consistency or the statistical nature.

6.4.1. Maximum cladding temperature

The simple rank correlation coefficients related to the maximum

⁵ Both simple and simple rank coefficients have been evaluated during this work. However, since the simple rank correlation coefficients reproduce the same qualitative trend of the simple correlation coefficient, only the simple rank correlation coefficients are shown in this work.

Fig. 6.5. Uncertainty width, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the maximum cladding temperature.

Fig. 6.6. Uncertainty width, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the core collapsed coolant level.

cladding temperature during each PhW are reported in Fig. 6.8, Fig. 6.9 and Fig. 6.10.

At the beginning of the PhW 1, a significant positive statistical correlation with decay power (P₁) is observed. This means that, as expected, an increase in decay power is reflected in an increase in the

maximum cladding temperature. It confirms the dominant role of residual core power in determining the initial thermal response of the fuel.

It is important to highlight the significant positive statistical correlation with the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (P₁₃) throughout the PhW 1. An increase in P₁₃ corresponds to a lower rate of depressurization of

Fig. 6.7. Uncertainty width, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of containment pressure.

Fig. 6.8. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the maximum cladding temperature during PhW 1.

the RPV and therefore to a delay of intervention of passive safety systems, leading to a worsening of the core cooling conditions and thus an increase in the maximum cladding temperature.

The heat transfer surface area of the EHRS heat exchangers (P_8) presents a significant negative statistical correlation. This is an expected result, as a decrease in P_8 leading worst core cooling conditions and therefore an increase in the maximum cladding temperature.

During PhW 2 and PhW 3, statistical correlations become dominated by uncertain input parameters associated with the passive safety systems' performance. In particular, P_13 and P_8 remain the uncertain input parameters with the most significant correlation, indicating that the long-term evolution of the maximum cladding temperature is mainly governed by the effectiveness of passive heat removal and

depressurization mechanisms rather than by the initial thermodynamic state of the system.

6.4.2. Collapsed coolant level in the core region

The simple rank correlation coefficients related to the collapsed coolant level in the core region during each PhW are reported in Fig. 6.11, Fig. 6.12 and Fig. 6.13.

During PhW 1, a significant positive statistical correlation is observed for the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (P_13). Higher P_13 values correspond to lower discharge of coolant inventory from the ADS Stage-1 valves, limiting the depressurization of the RPV and keeping the hot coolant within the core. It implies a delay in the activation of passive safety systems injection and a deterioration in core cooling conditions,

Fig. 6.9. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the maximum cladding temperature during PhW 2.

Fig. 6.10. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the maximum cladding temperature during PhW 3.

leading to an increase in the maximum cladding temperature, as discussed previously.

During PhW 1 and PhW 2, a positive significant statistical correlation with the initial containment pressure (P₅) is observed. Higher P₅ values tend to reduce the RPV depressurization, limiting the mass flow rate from the break and primary coolant inventory decreases, leading to an increase in the collapsed coolant level in the core region. The statistical correlation starts to be significant at about 1500 s after the SOT, when the system is not in choked flow conditions.

During PhW 3, the EHRS heat transfer surface (P₈) presents a significant positive statistical correlation. It implies that a higher value of P₈ implies a higher level in the core region. It highlights the key role of the energy removed by the passive decay heat removal system during PhW 3 in restoring the coolant level in the core region.

6.4.3. Containment pressure

The simple rank correlation coefficients related to the containment pressure during each PhW are reported in Fig. 6.14, Fig. 6.15 and Fig. 6.16.

During PhW 1, a significant positive statistical correlation is observed for the break flow discharge coefficient (P₉). Higher P₉ values increase the mass flow rate of primary coolant through the break, leading to a greater pressurization of the containment.

The ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (P₁₃) presents a significant negative statistical correlation with the containment pressure. Higher P₁₃ values limit the mass release rate into the containment, contributing to a reduction in containment pressurization during this phase, as expected. However, this statistical correlation changes during PhW 2 from negative to positive as the system approaches equalization between RPV and

Fig. 6.11. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the collapsed coolant level in the core region during PhW 1.

Fig. 6.12. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the collapsed coolant level in the core region during PhW 2.

containment. As discussed above, higher values of P₁₃ cause a limited depressurization of the RPV and a delay in the activation of passive safety systems, leading to a slower depressurization of the coupled primary containment system.

As expected, a significant positive statistical correlation is observed with the initial containment pressure (P₅). It should be noted that this correlation evolves during the PhW 1: as the blowdown progresses, the statistical correlation with P₅ gradually decreases since the phenomenology is mainly governed by the release of mass and energy from the break. Subsequently, the statistical correlation changes from low to moderate and then to significant.

During PhW 2 a significant negative statistical correlation is observed with the Heat Transfer Surface EHRs HXs (P₈). It is important to underline that during this phase, the EHRs system plays a key role in transferring primary energy from the RPV to the RWHS pool. Then, higher values of P₈ determine an increased energy transfer from the RPV to the EHRs system and then a reduction in the containment pressure, considering the RPV-Containment coupling.

Similar trends of the correlation coefficients are observed for the PhW 3. During this phase, the containment pressure evolution is fully governed by the operation of passive safety systems and heat removal.

Then, the influence of P₈ remains significant as well as the influence of P₁₃, with its indirect effect previously explained.

7. Conclusions

During the last years, the international nuclear scientific community has increasingly focused on evaluating the applicability of SA integral codes to light water SMRs designs. In this context, the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project, coordinated by ENEA, aims to assess the capabilities of both European and non-European computational tools in modelling SA scenarios in iPWR. These reactors are characterized by the adoption of passive safety systems and an integral configuration.

The activity presented in this work has been developed within the framework of the SASPAM-SA project with the aim of assessing the capabilities of the SA integral code MELCOR in simulating the thermal-hydraulic behaviour of a generic iPWR during a DBA scenario. In particular, a LOCA transient initiated by the double-ended guillotine rupture of the DVI injection line has been studied, and the uncertainty analysis adopting the BEPU approach has been applied to quantify the uncertainty in the code predictions. To achieve this, fourteen uncertain input parameters related to initial and boundary conditions and passive

Fig. 6.13. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the collapsed coolant level in the core region during PhW 3.

Fig. 6.14. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the containment pressure during PhW 1.

safety systems operation have been considered, and three safety-relevant FOMs have been selected: peak of maximum cladding temperature after 1000 s from the SOT, minimum collapsed coolant level in the core region and maximum containment pressure.

The analysis of the results demonstrates that the code is able to reproduce the typical phenomenology of the transient, which includes the blowdown, core reflooding and long-term cooling phases. The uncertainty analysis has permitted the estimation of the uncertainty width of the FOMs and their main statistical parameters such as mean, median, standard deviation and coefficient of variation. In particular, the FOMs are characterized by uncertainty width of 42.77 K, 0.7 m and 0.82E5 Pa, respectively.

To have insights about the code uncertainties along the simulated transient, the uncertainty width of the maximum cladding temperature, core collapsed coolant level and containment pressure at each time-step has been compared with the reference case and the main statistical parameters such as mean and median. Furthermore, the standard deviation and coefficient of variation have been calculated at each time step as well. This approach permitted the analysis of the variability of the uncertainty width along each PhW. In particular, an uncertainty of about 4000 s has been highlighted for the recovery time of the coolant level

above the TAF. Furthermore, an uncertainty width of 0.4 MPa has been observed for the peak containment pressure. In this regard, uncertainties on containment pressure influence the simulation of the activation of passive safety systems.

The computation of statistical correlation coefficients has been allowed for the identification of parameters showing moderate to significant correlation with the FOMs. In particular, the initial pressure of the containment presents a moderate statistical correlation with the minimum core collapsed level and with the maximum containment pressure. The heat transfer surface area of the EHRS HXs presents a moderate statistical correlation with the minimum core collapsed coolant level and maximum containment pressure, and a significant statistical correlation with the maximum cladding temperature. Finally, the ADS Stage-1 presents a significant statistical correlation with each FOM. The identification of the parameters with a moderate or significant statistical correlation with the FOMs highlights the need for particular attention for their modelling. In this regard, dedicated experimental campaigns could provide important additional data for these parameters, and code validation activities could be conducted. On the other hand, these parameters should be modelled with particular attention to the development of input decks. To better investigate the statistical

Fig. 6.15. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the containment pressure during PhW 2.

Fig. 6.16. Simple rank correlation coefficient for the containment pressure during PhW 3.

correlation characterizing the uncertain input parameters, the statistical correlation coefficient has been calculated at each time step. It permitted the analysis of the influence of these parameters on the maximum cladding temperature, the core collapsed coolant level and the containment pressure during each PhW.

In general, the present study demonstrates the applicability of the BEPU approach to IPWR designs. In particular, the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty represents the current state-of-the-art uncertainty methodology to characterize calculation uncertainties of thermal-hydraulic system codes and integral codes for the licensing of conventional LWRs calculations and benefits from a well-established know-how of the international community. The potential adoption of this consolidated approach for the future licensing of advanced LWR technologies may provide methodological continuity with existing practices. In this context, the results presented here provide important insights into uncertainties on safety-relevant FOMs, modelling strategies and assumptions, supporting future activities related to the use of these

codes in safety analyses.

Moreover, significant efforts have already been devoted to the application of the BEPU uncertainty methodology to integral system codes (such as in the EC MUSA project), making this approach a natural starting point for extending uncertainty quantification practices to postulated SA in advanced reactors. In this framework, future analyses should be carried out to extend the methodology to DEC conditions to further investigate the statistical relationship between uncertain input parameters and safety-relevant FOMs related to SAs, such as hydrogen and aerosol production.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- «INTERNATIONAL REACTOR INNOVATIVE AND SECURE, IRIS Plant Overview,» October 2002.
- Achilli, A., Congiu, C., Ferri, R., Bianchi, F., Meloni, P., Grgić, D., Dzodzo, M., 2012. SPES3 facility RELAP5 sensitivity analyses on the containment system for design review. *Sci. Technol. Nucl. Install.* 2012 (1), 173637.
- G. Agnello, M. Massone, F. Mascari, «Uncertainty quantification application on the Phebus FPT1 using the coupling of MELCOR and DAKOTA in a Python environment/architecture,» *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 441, n. 114135, 2025.
- G. Agnello, P.A. Di Maio, A. Bersano, F. Mascari, «Cold Leg LBLOCA uncertainty analysis using TRACE/DAKOTA coupling,» *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2177, n. 012023, 2022.
- F. Alcaro, A. Bersano, C. Bertani, F. Mascari, «BEPU analysis of a passive decay heat removal system with RELAP5/MOD3.3 and RELAP5-3D,» *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 136, n. 103724, 2021.
- A. Bersano, F. Mascari, M.T. Porfiri, P. Maccari, C. Bertani, «Ingress of Coolant Event simulation with TRACE code with accuracy evaluation and coupled DAKOTA Uncertainty Analysis,» *Fusion Engineering and Design*, vol. 159, n. 111944, 2020.
- A. Bersano, G. Agnello, P.A. Di Maio, G. Grippo, F. Mascari, «BEPU analysis of an Upgraded ICE facility test by TRACE/DAKOTA coupling,» *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2685, n. 012055, 2024.
- S. Brumm et al., «Uncertainty quantification for severe-accident reactor modelling: Results and conclusions of the MUSA reactor applications work package,» *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 211, n. 110962, 2025.
- M. Carrelli, L. Conway, M. Dzodzo, A. Maioli, L. Oriani, G. Storrck, B. Petrovic, A. Achilli, G. Cattadori, C. Congiu, R. Ferri, M. Ricotti, D. Papini, F. Bianchi, P. Meloni, S. Monti, F. Berra, D. Grgić, G. Yoder, A. Alamberti, «The SPES3 experimental facility design for the IRIS reactor simulation,» *Science and Technology of Nuclear Installations*, vol. vol2009, n. 579430, 2009.
- P. Chatelard, S. Belon, L. Bosland, L. Carénini, O. Coindreau, F. Cousin, C. Marchetto, H. Nowack, L. Piar, L. Chalain, «Main modelling features of the ASTEC V2.1 major version,» *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. Vol. 93, pp. 83-93, 2016.
- Y.J. Chung, S.W. Lim, K.H. Bae, «Investigation of TASS/SMR capability to predict a natural circulation in the test facility for an integral reactor,» *Science and Technology of Nuclear Installations*, vol. vol. 2014, n. 181802, 2014.
- O. Coindreau et al., «Uncertainty quantification for a severe accident sequence in a SFP in the frame of the H-2020 project MUSA: First outcomes,» *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 188, n. 109796, 2023.
- European Commission, «European Industrial Alliance on Small Modular Reactors,» Accessed: May 20, 2025.
- ETSON, SASPAM-SA, [Online]. Available: <https://www.etsn.eu/node/290>.
- European Commission, EASI-SMR, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101164810>.
- European Commission, ELSMOR, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/847553>.
- European Commission, HARMONIZE, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101061643>.
- European Commission, MCSAFER, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/945063>.
- European Commission, PASTELS, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/945275>.
- European Commission, SASPAM-SA, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059853>.
- European Commission, TANDEM, [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059479>.
- R. Ferri, «SPES3-IRIS facility RELAP5 sensitivity analyses on the containment system for design review,» no. SIET 01 526 RT 09 Rev.0, 2010.
- R. Ferri, C. Congiu, «Conceptual design of SPES3-IRIS facility,» SIET 01 334 RT 07 Rev.1, Piacenza (Italy), 2008.
- Ferri, R., Achilli, A., Cattadori, G., Bianchi, F., Meloni, P., 2005. Design, experiments and Relap5 code calculations for the perseo facility. *Nucl. Eng. Des.* 235, 1201–1214.
- F. Gabrielli, M. Di Giuli, M. Malicki, A. Bersano, P. Maccari, F. Giannetti, «Generic Data on Design 1 and Design 2,» SASPAM-SA, Milestone Version 0.3 (DRAFT), 2024.
- K.A. Gamble, L.P. Swiler, «Uncertainty Quantification and Sensitivity Analysis Applications to Fuel Performance Modeling,» SAND2016-4597C, 2016.
- M. Garbarini, G. Agnello, A. Bersano, F. Gabrielli, L. Luzzi, F. Mascari, «Simulation of QUENCH-06 Experiment by MELCOR v2.2 with Uncertainty Analysis,» *Nuclear Technology*, pp. 1-20.
- H. Glaeser, «GRS Method for Uncertainty and Sensitivity Evaluation of Code Results and Applications,» *Science and Technology of Nuclear Installations*, vol. Volume 2008, n. 798901, 2008.
- A. Guba, M. Makai, L. Pal, «Statistical aspects of best estimate method-L,» *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, vol. 80, pp. 217-232, 2003.
- L.E. Herranz, S. Beck, V.H. Sánchez-Espinoza, F. Mascari, S. Brumm, O. Coindreau, S. Paci, «The EC MUSA Project on Management and Uncertainty of Severe Accidents: Main Pillars and Status,» *Energies*, vol. 14(15), n. 4473, 2021.
- L.E. Herranz, S. Beck, V.H. Sánchez-Espinoza, F. Mascari, S. Brumm, O. Coindreau, S. Paci, «Major Achievements of the EC MUSA Project,» *Nuclear Technology*, pp. 1-11, 2025.
- L.E. Herranz, B. Poubeau, L. Chailan, F. Mascari, «Looking ahead to severe accident research,» *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.*, vol. 11, n. 28, 2025.
- L.L. Humphries, B.A. Beeny, F. Gelbard, T. Haskin, J. Phillips, J. Reynolds, R.C. Schmidt, «MELCOR Computer Code Manuals: Vol. 1: Primer and User's Guide Version 2.2 r2023.0,» Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque (USA), 2023.
- L.L. Humphries, B.A. Beeny, F. Gelbard, T. Haskin, D. Louie, J. Phillips, J. Reynolds, R.C. Schmidt, «MELCOR Computer Code Manuals: Vol. 2: Reference Manual Version 2.2 r2023.0,» Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque (USA), 2023.
- IAEA, [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/projects/crp/i31033>.
- iaea, 1996. Defence in Depth in Nuclear Safety. INSAG-10.
- iaea, 2005. «Innovative small and Medium Sized Reactors: Design Features. Safety Approaches and r&d Trends,».
- iaea, 2008. «Safety Reports Series No. 52: best Estimate Safety Analysis for Nuclear Power Plants. Uncertainty Evaluation,» Vienna.
- IAEA, «Advancing the State of the Practice in Uncertainty and Sensitivity Methodologies for Severe Accident Analysis in Water Cooled Reactors in the QUENCH-06 Experiment,» IAEA-TECDOC-2045, 2024.
- Applied Programming Technology Inc., «Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package (SNAP) User's Manual,» 2021.
- A. Kecek, Z. Parduba, «Simulation of PASI experiment on passive containment heat removal system with MELCOR and ATHLET,» in *Proceedings of the International Conference Nuclear Energy for New Europe*, Portorož, Slovenia, September 11-14, 2023.
- P. Maccari, M. Massone, A. Bersano, F. Mascari, A. Cervone, S. Manservisi, «ASTEC-RAVEN coupling for uncertainty analysis of an ingress of coolant event in fusion plants,» *Fusion Engineering and Design*, vol. 169, n. 112442, 2021.
- P. Maccari, F. Mascari, S. Ederli, P. Meloni, S. Manservisi, «ASTEC code DBA analysis of passive mitigation strategy on a generic IRIS SMR,» *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 156, n. 108194, 2021.
- P. Maccari, J.A. Zambaux, A. Bersano, «BEPU analysis of a 2-in DVI break in a generic IRIS SMR by ASTEC - RAVEN coupling,» *EUROSAFE Forum 2021*, Paris, France, November 22-23, 2021.
- P. Maccari, G. Agnello, F. Mascari, S. Ederli, «Analysis of BDBA sequences in a generic IRIS reactor using ASTEC code,» *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 182, n. 109611, 2023.
- P. Maccari, A. Bersano, S. Ederli, F. Gabrielli, F. Mascari, «Validation and uncertainty analysis of ASTEC in early degradation phase against QUENCH-06 experiment,» *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 414, n. 112600, 2023.
- M. Malicki, T. Lind, «MELCOR 2.2 iPWR LOCA type accident analysis, PART I: Thermal-hydraulics,» *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 428, n. 113433, 2024.
- M. Malicki, T. Lind, «MELCOR 2.2 iPWR LOCA type accident analysis, PART II: BDBA,» *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 430, n. 113667, 2024.
- F. Mascari, G. Vella, B.G. Woods, F. D'Auria, «Analyses of the OSU-MASLWR Experimental Test Facility,» *Science and Technology of Nuclear Installations*, vol. vol. 2012, n. 528241, 2012.
- F. Mascari, F. De Rosa, B.G. Woods, K. Welter, G. Vella, F. D'Auria, «Analysis of the OSU-MASLWR 001 and 002 Tests by Using the TRACE Code,» NUREG/IA-0466, 2016.
- F. Mascari et al., «OECD/NEA/CSNI/WGAMA PERSEO benchmark: Main outcomes and conclusions,» *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 405, n. 112220, 2023.
- Mascari, F., Vella, G., Woods, B.G., Welter, K., Pottorf, J., Young, E., Adorni, M., D'Auria, F., 2011. Sensitivity analysis of the MASLWR helical coil steam generator using TRACE. *Nucl. Eng. Des.* 241, 1137–1144.
- F. Mascari, H. Nakamura, K. Umminger, F. De Rosa, F. D'Auria, «Scaling issues for the experimental characterization of reactor coolant system in integral test facilities and role of system code as extrapolation tool,» Vol. %1 di %2NURETH-16, August 30 - September 4, 2015.

- F. Mascari et al., «Euratom SASPAM-SA project: main ideas and first outcomes,» in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Small Modular Reactors and their Applications*, 2024.
- F. Mascari et al., «Main outcomes of the Phebus FPT1 uncertainty and sensitivity analysis in the EU-MUSA project,» *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 196, n. 110205, 2024.
- Nucleareurope, European SMR pre-Partnership, [Online]. Available: <https://www.nucleareurope.eu/project/european-smr-pre-partnership/>.
- H.S. Park, S.K. Moon, Y.S. Kim, S. Cho, K.Y. Choi, H. Bae, D.E. Kim, N.H. Choi, K.H. Min, Y.J. Ko, Y.C. Shin, R.J. Park, W.J. Lee, C.H. Song, S.J. Yi, «An Integral Effect Test Facility of the SMART, SMART-ITL,» in *Transaction of the Korean Nuclear Society Autumn Meeting*, Gyeongju, Korea, October 25-26, 2012.
- H.S. Park, B.Y. Min, Y.G. Jung, Y.C. Shin, Y.J. Ko, S.J. Yi, «Design of the VISTA-ITL Test Facility for an Integral Type Reactor of SMART and a Post-Test Simulation of a SBLOCA Test,» *Science and Technology of Nuclear Installation*, vol. Volume 2014, n. 840109, 2014.
- Perez, M., et al., 2011. Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis of a LBLOCA in a PWR Nuclear Power Plant: results of the phase V of the BEMUSE programme. *Nucl. Eng. Des.* 241, 4206–4222.
- J. Pottorf, F. Mascari, B.G. Woods, «TRACE, RELAP5 Mod 3.3, and RELAP5-3D Code Comparison of OSU-MASLWR-001 Test,» *2009 ANS Winter Meeting and Nuclear Technology Expo. Transactions of the ANS. ISSN: 0003-018X*, vol. Volume 101, 2009.
- M. Principato, F. Giannetti, M. Imperatori, M. D'Onorio, M. Garcia, L.E. Herranz, A. Bersano, F. Mascari, «Analyses of the MELCOR capability to simulate integral PWR using passive systems in a DBA scenario,» *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 437, n. 114004, 2025.
- Rodgers, J.L., Nicewander, A., 1987. Thirteen Ways to look at the Correlation Coefficient. *The American Statistician* 42, 59–66.
- SAFETY ANALYSIS OF SMR WITH PASSIVE MITIGATION STRATEGIES - SEVERE ACCIDENT (SASPAM-SA), [Online]. Available: <https://www.saspam-sa.eu/>.
- SMR Regulators' Forum, «Pilot Project Report: Considering the Application of a Graded Approach, Defence-in-Depth and Emergency Planning Zone Size for Small Modular Reactors,» 2018.
- Stephens, M.E., Goodwin, B.W., Andres, T.H., 1993. Deriving parameter probability density functions. *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 42, 271–291.
- Applied Programming Technology, Inc., *AptPlot User's Manual*, 2021.
- Wald, A., 1943. An extension of Wilks' method for setting tolerance limits. *Ann. Math. Stat.* 14, 45–55.
- Wilks, S.S., 1941. Determination of sample size for setting tolerance limits. *Ann. Math. Stat.* 12, 91–96.
- Wilks, S.S., 1942. Statistical prediction with special reference to the problem of tolerance limits. *Ann. Math. Stat.* 13, 400–409.
- Yoon, D.S., Jo, H., Fu, W., Wu, Q., Corradini, M.L., 2017. «MELCOR Analysis of OSU Multi-Application Small Light Water Reactor (MASLWR). Experiment,» *Nuclear Technology* 198 (3), 277–292.
- Zenodo, SASPAM-SA, [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/communities/saspam-sa/about>.